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ADJUSTMENT OF THE POPULATION'S NUTRITIONAL STATUS BY FUNCTIONAL FOODS

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Abstract

The article discusses production of the functional foods from natural, non-traditional ecologically pure raw materials. It considers the issue of maintaining properties of biologically active substances used as ingredients in the functional foods production to maximal possible extent. Attention is focused on adequately selected methods for studying of biochemical characteristics of the raw materials for production of functional foods. Advantage of consumption of the functional foods compared with the food supplements used in the diet is established. Functional food and ingredients allow adjustment of the nutritional status of individuals (athletes).

Keywords: athlete, nutritional status, non-traditional raw materials, functional food.

Introduction

One of the key objectives of the state policies in the sphere of healthy nutrition is production of the food enriched with the permanent ingredients. Among them the most significant are: specialized baby food, functional products, dietary (therapeutic and preventive food products and biologically active food supplements necessary for maintenance and strengthening of the population's health, for reduction of the risks of different diseases caused by inadequate and unbalanced nutrition and their prevention.

Functional food products with the scientifically grounded and proven properties are the special food products suitable for systematic use in the diet of all age groups of the healthy population [4].

They reduce risks of diseases related to nutrition, reduce or compensate deficiency of nutrients in food products (due to presence of functional ingredients), to maintain and improve human health [2].

Functional food ingredients include physiologically active ingredients that are good for human health and that are safe, with known physical and chemical characteristics with identified and scientifically proven biochemical and physiological qualities for health maintenance and improvement.

Research Goal

Research goal was collection of the available materials about functional ingredients and food, as well as about biologically active supplements. Provide their comparison, with respect of their consumption and demand for them at world market. Associate them with the population's nutrition status and, on the basis of analysis, make relevant conclusions.

Materials and Methods

We have collected relevant materials about functional food and ingredients. We have also collected the materials about biologically active supplements and usual supplements.

Research Results and Discussion

It is well known that the food supplements are different from the biologically active supplements and products with functional properties and the difference is that the latter are not intended to have the properties that contribute to prevention or treatment of the diseases in humans.

Food supplements are the products intended for supplementing normal diet. They comprise the concentrated sources of the nutrients (vitamins and minerals) or of the other substances with high nutritive value and physiological effect.

For last 20 years, annual growth of the food supplements and dietary supplements is 7-10%. In many developed countries, at least 70% of the population consumes food supplements, dietary supplements and functional food [1]. In the economically advanced countries (e.g. in EU countries), up to 25% of the food produced at industrial scale, are the functional products (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Population's demand: 1- food supplements, 2 – functional food products.

It is clear from the figure that today, at the world market the demand for functional food products is higher than that for the common food supplements. Consequently, the conclusion can be made that the functional food products can be used for adjustment of the population's nutritional status.

It should be noted that the athlete's food is included into the basic list for which the functional food products could be allowed. Today, overall, in the world, four groups of functional food products are widespread [3, 5] (Fig. 2).

Natural functional food products include the products prepared from natural vegetable and/or animal raw materials, through fermentation, to ensure that the end products contain no less that 15% of the natural functional ingredients, corresponding to the daily requirement of natural functional food ingredients per portion. Natural functional food products do not contain the products obtained by gene modification technologies. Functional food is produced as a result of reduction of the harmful ingredients in the traditional foods and their enrichment with the functional ingredients.

Figure 2. Key groups of functional food products

Based on the conducted study, we can make the following conclusions: 1. Functional food must be produced of the ecologically pure raw materials of natural vegetable and/or animal origin, through fermentation. 2. It is established that consumption of functional food is more advantageous than food supplements in the diet. 3. Functional food and ingredients allow adjustment of the nutritional status of individuals (athletes).

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